

Original Research Article

Effectiveness of an Educational Program about Breast Cancer and Breast Cancer Self-examination on Knowledge among Women in AlJeeraif West Administrative Unit 2017

Amel Eltaib Elagib¹, Ibrahim Ismail M. Abu^{2,3*}, Samia Yousif Idris Habbani⁴,
Gaafer Abelrahman Omaar³

Abstract

¹Fedral Ministry of Health, Khartoum, Khartoum State, Sudan

²Faculty of Medicine, King Abdelaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

³Faculty of Medicine, AL-Fashir University, North Darfur State, Sudan

⁴Free Lance Community Medicine Consultant, Khartoum, Sudan

*Corresponding Authors Email: burha75@gmail.com

The aim of this study is to assess the baseline knowledge about breast cancer and breast self-examination (BSE) and to find out the effectiveness of an educational program about breast cancer and BSE on knowledge among women in AlJeeraif West Administrative Unit. Community based intervention study with pre-post and control was carried out among 200 women in AlJeeraif West Administrative Unit. Two hundred women were recruited by means of multistage sampling. The sample size was divided equally into intervention and control groups. Baseline data was collected from both groups through face to face interview, using structured close ended questionnaire. Educational program was implemented for the intervention group. Four months after the intervention, women in the study and control groups were exposed to the same questionnaire. Chi-square, paired t-test and independent t-test (difference of difference) were conducted in the course of the data analyses. Statistically significant difference exists in the intervention group pre-post program (p value 0.000) in basic, symptoms, risk factors and overall knowledge. Statistically significant differences exist in the mean difference of knowledge between the intervention and control groups (p-value .000). The results of this study have confirmed the effectiveness of educational program on improving knowledge of breast cancer and BSE

Keywords: Breast cancer, Breast self-examination, Health belief model, Health education, AlJeeraif West

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the second most common cancer in the world and the most common cancer among women, with an estimated 1.67 million new cancer cases diagnosed in 2012 (25% of all cancers) (Ferlay et al., 2015). Cancer global statistics revealed that there is a rising incidence of breast cancer making it the commonest cancer, not only in the developed countries but also in the developing world. Worldwide over 1.5 million women are diagnosed with breast cancer and 502,000 die from the disease

each year (Ghaffari et al., 2014). The incidence of breast cancer in African countries (reported to be 23 per 100,000) is lower than overall rates in North America or Western Europe, as well as lower than rates among black women residing in these Western countries. Local registries in Africa report a doubling of rates over the past 40 years (Porter, 2008). Incidence rates were higher in more developed countries compared to less developed countries (71.7/100,000 and 29.3/100,000 respectively,

adjusted to the World 2000 Standard Population) whereas the corresponding mortality rates were 17.1/100,000 and 11.8/100,000, with the differential linked to a combination of early detection, access to treatment services and cultural barriers (Youlten et al., 2012). Breast cancer survival rates vary greatly worldwide, ranging from 80% or over in developed countries to less than 40% in low-income countries (Al-Sharbatti et al., 2013) in low and middle-income countries Breast cancer has a low cure rate because patients often present with late-stage disease that has metastasized to other organs (Abuidris et al., 2013). Poorer outcomes in low- and middle-income countries may be due to their healthcare systems having a limited capacity for successful early detection, diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer (Ozmen and Anderson, 2008). According to Globocan estimates, the most common cancers in both sexes are breast cancer, non-Hodgkin lymphoma, leukemia, esophagus, and colorectal cancer (Elamin et al., 2015). Breast cancer is a major killer of women both globally and regionally. Most patients with breast cancer in the region present for the first time at stages two and three, indicating the need for increased community awareness and early detection of the disease (Organization, 2006). Early detection is the identification of breast cancer at a stage where the treatment has the greatest chance of producing cure. It remains the main strategy and helps to decrease mortality and morbidity from breast cancer (Yip et al., 2008). Public awareness and education in BSE can have tremendous impact on early identification, diagnosis, treatment and consequently survival from breast cancer.

Educational interventions can enhance women's knowledge regarding the importance of breast cancer and its' screening methods. Also these education programs could improve the behaviors of individuals regarding BSE. Lack of knowledge and wrong beliefs regarding the importance of regular BSE could have an effect on not to perform BSE. Thus designing suitable educational interventions could promote this screening healthy behavior among women (Aghamolaei et al., 2011).

In Sudan, cancer incidence has been growing at an average annual rate of 0.061 over the last five decades 1967–2010 and is likely to continue to grow (Elamin et al., 2015). The data from National Cancer Registry (NCR) indicated that prostate and breast are the most commonly diagnosed cancer in men and women respectively in Khartoum, and that breast cancer is the most common cancer with an incidence rate of 25.1 per100,000 (Saeed et al., 2014).

In many countries cancer may carry a stigma that prevents people from seeking medical care. In Sudan, there is a common perception that cancer is transmissible, leading to isolation of patients and breakdown of marriages, which may lead patients to hesitate to seek proper care. Due to lack of awareness

about the signs and symptoms of cancer many people do not present to medical care until they have very advanced disease (Coates, 1999).

A total of 78% of Sudanese patients have stage III or IV disease when they first seek medical treatment (Hamad, 2006). In these stages, treatment may often involve multiple modalities, including surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy and hormone therapy, and has a markedly diminished chance of success. Therefore, there is an urgent need for better early detection of cancer in Sudan to make treatment more effective, not expensive, need minor surgery, and access to treatment services and acceptable to patients (Coates, 1999).

Problem Statement

Breast cancer is the commonest cancer among women in Sudan. It accounts for 16.12% of all cancers (30.24% of all female cancers in 2006 (Ahmed et al., 2010). It occurs at a younger age compared to Western Women, as about 40% of the patients are below the age of 45 years and mean age of 50 years. Most of the patients present with stages 3 and 4 (Ahmed and Elnimeiri, 2013).

Lack of knowledge about this disease leads breast cancer patients to seek medical care at late stages, when the cancer is very advanced, at which point their chance of getting successful treatment is substantially reduced (Ahmed and Elnimeiri, 2013).

Breast cancer mortality is high in Sudan and most patients are detected at late stages of the disease, due to the lack of awareness and absence of screening programs (Norman and Brain, 2005).

Rationale

The low survival rates in less developed countries explained mainly by lack of early detection program, which results in a high proportion of women presenting with late stage disease (Farma et al., 2014).

Public awareness and education in BSE can have great impact on early identification, diagnosis, treatment and consequently survival from breast cancer (Ahmed and Elnimeiri, 2013).

METHODS

Study design

This is a community based intervention study pre-intervention-post intervention education program with control.

Study area

The study was conducted in AlJeeraif West administrative unit; it is one of the old Administrative units of Khartoum Locality, it located in east Khartoum and divided into six Haras. Its population is about (44800) formed of many tribes and also inhabited by a lot of foreigner. AlShaheed Abu Dojana health center provides health services.

Study Population

Women aged (20-65) resident in AlJeeraif West.

Inclusion criteria

Women aged 20-65 years who were available at the time of study and accept to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria

- Women who are difficult to communicate with them (deaf, with severe mental illness, etc)
- Severely ill patients.
- Women who had history of breast cancer
- Non Sudanese women resident in Eljeeraif West

Sampling

Sampling technique

Multistage sampling technique

Sample size

The sample size was calculated Using this formula:-

$$n = \frac{((1 - \alpha/2) \sqrt{2P(1-P)} + 1 - P \sqrt{P(1-P)} + 2(P-0.2))^2}{(\Delta)^2}$$

Where:

n=sample size

P=.5

Z $1 - \alpha/2$ = area of 95% under the normal curve =1.96

Z $1 - \beta/2$ =the power of 80%=.84

Proportions were estimated from a previous study conducted in Gezira State, in which, 12% of women adhered to practicing BSE prior to education intervention regarding breast cancer and 33% post intervention (Abdelrahman and Ahmed, 2006).

P1=the pre knowledge from previous study =.12

P2= the post knowledge test .33

$$\Delta = P1 - P2 =$$

Thus the sample size was 100 women for the study group and another 100 for the control group. The sample size was distributed to the two hara in study group by using probability proportion to size, the households and women were chosen by the same way as for the control group.

Sampling Technique

Regarding the study group a total of two (Haras) were selected by using the computer probability proportion to size (PPS), and each Haras was consisted of number of households proportional to the percentage of households in hara. The first household was selected using random computer table; the subsequent houses were selected according to the interval which was calculated to be 20. If the data collectors found more than one woman fulfilled the inclusion criteria in the selected house, he will selected one randomly, and if there was no woman in the selected house or no woman fulfilled the inclusion criteria, he will moved to the next house and so on. The control was from 5th and 6th Haras in Eljeeraif West administration unit, which were far away and more or less similar to the study group. The households and women were chosen by the same way as for the study group.

Data collection tools and Techniques

Data was collected through face to face interview using structured close ended questionnaire. The duration of data collection was two weeks before intervention and two weeks after it

Data management and analysis

Data collected was cleaned in the field for consistency and completeness by researcher. It was coded, tabulated and analyzed by statistician using computer package with the software: SPSS version 20.

The data obtained by questionnaire was analyzed based on the set of objectives of the study using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Descriptive statistics, such as percentages, frequencies, means, and standard deviations, were used to measure the socio- demographic variables and the responses to knowledge.

The knowledge was measured using multiple choice questions and one correct answer. Each item regarding the knowledge was scored one when correctly answered and others as zero.. Analytical statistics such as paired test, t-test and chi-square test were used to determine pre- post intervention change in knowledge about breast cancer and BSE, Independent t-test (difference of difference) was used to compare the mean difference between the intervention and control groups pre-post

Table 1. Distribution of study sample according to socio-demographic characteristics in AlJeeraif West Administrative Unit, 2017 (n=200)

Socio-demographic characteristics	Women			P-value	
	Control group		Intervention group		Total
	N	(%)	N (%)		N (%)
Age	20_29	24 (24)	27 (27.3)	51 (25.6)	0.477
	30_39	27 (27)	23 (23.2)	50 (25.1)	
	40_49	21 (21)	28 (28.3)	49 (24.6)	
	50_60	28 (28)	22(21.2)	50 (24.7)	
	Total	100 (100)	100 (100)	200(100)	
Education level	Basic	18 (18)	19 (19)	37 (18.5)	0.189
	Secondary	28 (28)	39 (39)	67 (33.5)	
	University	54 (54)	42 (42)	96 (48)	
	Total	100 (100)	100 (100)	200 (100)	
Employment	House wife	57 (57)	64 (64)	121 (60.5)	0.079
	Student	14 (14)	15 (15)	29 (14.5)	
	Employee	28 (28)	15 (15)	43 (21.5)	
	Free business	1 (1)	3 (3)	4 (2)	
	Retired	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	
	other (mention)	0 (0)	3 (3)	3 (1.5)	
	Total	100 (100)	100 (100)	200 (100)	
Family monthly income in SDG	Less than 1000	7 (7)	26 (26)	33 (16.2)	0.004
	1000-1500	76 (76)	58(58)	134 (67.5)	
	1500-3000	16 (16)	14 (14)	30(14.7)	
	More than 3000	1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (1.5)	
	Total	100 (100)	100 (100)	200 (100)	

program. Statistical significance was < 0.05 for all analyses.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from Sudan Medical Specialization Board (SMSB) and Khartoum State Ministry of Health (KSMOH).

Informed consent was taken before any subject was enrolled in the study (Annex5). The participants were informed about the aim and potential benefit of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation and their right to access the research findings before giving verbal consent. They have the full autonomy and freedom to change their minds and withdraw at any time, without giving a reason. All the participants were informed that this survey is completely anonymous, the name, or any other identity information will not be used for any purpose other than this study. The privacy and confidentiality of the data was ensured.

RESULTS

Response rate

All participants, both in the control and intervention areas responded to the study pre and post to the intervention, thus giving a response rate of 100%.

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Table 1 show that almost all participants were distributed to the four age groups. Majority of them 44.7% had university education, 60.5% were unemployed, 67.5% having family monthly income of (1000-1500) Sudanese Pond (SDG). No statistically significant differences existed between the intervention and control groups with regard to socio-demographic variables, except for the family monthly income (P-value 0.004).

Knowledge

It has been found that all participants in both intervention and control groups had heard about breast cancer.

Figure 1 indicate that the most common sources of information for breast cancer among participants were mass media (41.0%) followed by relatives and friends (37.0%), While health worker accounts for only (3.5%).

Figure 2 shows that knowledge about symptoms and risk factors of breast cancer increased by 29.2% and 32.1% in the intervention group respectively which was statistically significant (p-value.000), where as in the control group there was no statistical significance.

Figure 3 shows that the knowledge about the best time to do BSE during the month increased by 86% in the intervention group, while in the control group it increased

Figure 1. Source of information about breast cancer among study sample, atA lJeeeraif West Administrative Unit, 2017 (n=200)

Figure 2. Knowledge about symptoms and risk factors of breast cancer among study sample, atAlJeeeraif West Administrative Unit, 2017 (n=200)

Figure 3. Knowledge about the best time to do BSE during the month among study sample, at AlJeeraif West Administrative Unit, 2017 (n=200)

Table 2. Pre-post intervention Change in basic knowledge, symptoms knowledge, risk factors knowledge and overall Knowledge among study sample, at AlJeeraif West Administrative Unit, 2017 (n=200)

Knowledge	Control group			Intervention group		
	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-value	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-value
Basic knowledge pre	56.3333	25.37928	0.642	65.8333	27.25519	0.000
Basic knowledge post	55.8333	25.22347		97.0000	9.87577	
symptoms knowledge pre	43.3333	22.22222	0.863	56.0000	28.47804	0.000
symptoms knowledge post	43.1667	22.36005		85.1667	16.22219	
Risk factor knowledge pre	30.1538	12.92174	0.854	43.3846	21.24340	0.000
Risk factor knowledge post	30.0769	13.12437		75.4615	17.41446	
BSE knowledge pre	35.7778	28.18799	0.114	42.6667	26.55420	0.000
BSE knowledge post	34.6667	27.90789		71.1111	16.48801	
Overall knowledge pre	38.5882	16.59721	0.414	49.3824	19.31282	0.000
Overall knowledge post	38.1471	16.50310		79.8235	13.83973	

by 44% post intervention.

Table 2. indicates that statistically significant difference exists in the intervention group

DISCUSSION

Public awareness and education in BSE can have great impact on early identification, diagnosis, treatment and consequently survival from breast cancer (Ahmed and Elnimeiri, 2013).

The aim of this study is to assess the baseline knowledge about breast cancer and breast self-examination and to find out the effectiveness of an educational program about breast cancer and BSE on knowledge.

The response rate of the participation both in the intervention and control areas was 100% and also the participation of the women in the intervention area in the education session was full for the whole five days. This indicates that the women are highly enthusiastic and motivated to participate in issues concerning their health

specially in regarding cancers. The study revealed that there was no significant difference between the intervention and control groups in most socio-demographic-characteristics. This finding ensures the similarity of the intervention and control groups.

The study indicated that all the women in the control and intervention areas had heard of breast cancer and mass media represented the most common source of information for breast cancer among participants. This finding is consistent with previous studies in Hong Kong (Yan, 2009), Sudan (Hussien et al., 2017), Zagazig (Mohammad et al., 2013) Iran (Hajian et al., 2011). Relatives and friend represented the second source of information whereas health care providers were the least, although they are supposed to play a major role in teaching, counseling and convincing women to practice BSE. This result may be due to the low implementation of the national strategy, healthcare systems having a limited capacity, insufficient numbers of appropriately trained healthcare workers and in availability of a resource center and may be careless of the participants in seeking proper medical advice.

Although all women had heard about BC, yet the study revealed that the majority of the participants had poor knowledge about breast cancer and breast Self-examination before the intervention program. Four months after the education program the breast cancer and BSE knowledge in the intervention group was significantly increased, while in the control group there was no significant difference. Also the mean difference in knowledge between the intervention and control group was significantly different, this significant difference proved that the educational program had a positive impact on increasing breast cancer and BSE knowledge among the intervention group, This finding is in consistence with those of the previous studies in Turkey (Secginli and Nahcivan, 2011), Korean- American (Lee, 2011), Iran (Farma et al., 2014).

In conclusion, the results of this study demonstrated the effectiveness of education program in promoting knowledge. Moreover, the comparative analyses of the two groups of this study showed effectiveness of the intervention in improving knowledge of BSE in intervention group compared to those in control group. These results are inconsistency with many previous study conducted worldwide.

This program was done with help of expert volunteer women from (Mubadarat Innovation Group). Their role in raising awareness about breast cancer and BSE among the women in AlJeeraif West Administrative Unit is highly appreciated. Thus using volunteer women may be effective strategy for raising women awareness

CONCLUSION

This study has confirmed the effectiveness of educational

program in promotion of knowledge about breast cancer and BSE, Limited knowledge available for study participants was mainly from mass media, relatives and friends, with only extremely limited role of health personnel. This indicates that the national cancer control strategy is not well implemented in the study area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Federal and states ministries of health should implement programs for BSE and they should encourage the role of mass media in promoting healthy positive behavior toward BSE and encourage and train volunteer women to make them competent in raising women awareness about breast cancer and early detection. The role of health care providers as an information sources about breast cancer should be increased. Regular follow up of the same study participants for longer time to identify the effect of time on retention of the adopted knowledge of the participants is needed.

REFERENCES

- Abdelrahman SA, Ahmed MAH (2006). Self examination of breast for early detection of breast cancer. *Sudanese J. Pub. Health Jan.* 1:1-88.
- Abuidris DO, Elsheikh A, Ali M, Musa H, Elgaili E, Ahmed AO, et al. (2013). Breast-cancer screening with trained volunteers in a rural area of Sudan: a pilot study. *The lancet oncology.* 14(4):363-70.
- Aghamolaei T, Hasani L, Tavafian SS, Zare S (2011). Improving breast self-examination: An educational intervention based on health belief model. *Iranian Journal of Cancer Prevention.* 4(2): 82-7.
- Ahmed H, Ali A, Almobarak A (2010). Frequency of breast cancer among Sudanese patients with breast palpable lumps. *Indian journal of cancer.* 47(1):23.
- Ahmed IH, Elnimeiri MKM (2013). Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Sudanese Women in Reproductive age (15–49 years) towards Breast Self-Examination.
- Al-Sharbatti SS, Shaikh RB, Mathew E, Al-Biate MAS (2013). Breast self examination practice and breast cancer risk perception among female university students in Ajman. *Asian Pacific J. Cancer Prevention.* 14(8):4919-23.
- Coates AS (1999). Breast cancer: delays, dilemmas, and delusions. *The Lancet.* 353(9159):1112-3.
- Elamin A, Ibrahim ME, Abuidris D, Mohamed KEH, Mohammed SI (2015). Part I: cancer in Sudan—burden, distribution, and trends breast, gynecological, and prostate cancers. *Cancer medicine.* 4(3):447-56.
- Farma KKF, Jalili Z, Zareban I, Pour MS (2014). Effect of education on preventive behaviors of breast cancer in female teachers of guidance schools of Zahedan city based on health belief model. *J. Edu. Health promotion.* 3.
- Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Dikshit R, Eser S, Mathers C, Rebelo M, et al. (2015). Cancer incidence and mortality worldwide: sources, methods and major patterns in GLOBOCAN 2012. *Int. J. Cancer.* 136(5).

- Ghaffari F, Shali M, Shoghi M, Joolae S (2014). Psychometric properties of the persian version of the self-assessed support needs questionnaire for breast cancer cases. *APJCP*. 15(3):1435-40.
- Hajian S, Vakilian K, Najabadi KM, Hosseini J, Mirzaei HR (2011). Effects of education based on the health belief model on screening behavior in high risk women for breast cancer, Tehran, Iran. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 12(1):49-54.
- Hamad H (2006). Cancer initiatives in Sudan. *Annals of oncology*. 17:viii32-viii6.
- Hussien RA, Abusalih HH, Hussein A (2017). The effect of awareness program on knowledge and practice regarding breast cancer early detection among women at Wad Nubai, in Omdurman locality, North Sudan. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*. 4(7):2938-42.
- Lee C (2011). The Impact of Breast Cancer Educational Workshops on Knowledge and Breast Self-Examination Practice among Korean-American Women.
- Mohammad FA, Bayoumi MM, Megahed MM (2013). Efficacy of Instructional Training Program in Breast Self-Examination & Breast Screening for Cancer among University Students. *Public Health Research*. 3(3):71-8.
- Norman P, Brain K (2005). An application of an extended health belief model to the prediction of breast self-examination among women with a family history of breast cancer. *British journal of health psychology*. 10(1):1-16.
- Organization WH (2006). Guidelines for the early detection and screening of breast cancer.
- Ozmen V, Anderson BO (2008). The challenge of breast cancer in low-and middle-income countries—implementing the breast health global initiative guidelines. *US Oncology, Touch briefing*. 76:79.
- Porter P (2008). “Westernizing” women's risks? Breast cancer in lower-income countries. *New Eng. J. Med*. 358(3):213-6.
- Saeed IE, Weng HY, Mohamed KH, Mohammed SI (2014). Cancer incidence in Khartoum, Sudan: first results from the Cancer Registry, 2009–2010. *Cancer medicine*. 3(4):1075-84.
- Secginli S, Nahcivan NO (2011). The effectiveness of a nurse-delivered breast health promotion program on breast cancer screening behaviours in non-adherent Turkish women: A randomized controlled trial. *International journal of nursing studies*. 48(1):24-36.
- Yan YY (2009). Breast cancer: knowledge and perceptions of Chinese women in Hong Kong. *Global journal of health science*.;1(2):97.
- Yip CH, Smith RA, Anderson BO, Miller AB, Thomas DB, Ang ES, et al. (2008). Guideline implementation for breast healthcare in low-and middle-income countries. *Cancer*. 113(S8):2244-56.
- Youlden DR, Cramb SM, Dunn NA, Muller JM, Pyke CM, Baade PD (2012). The descriptive epidemiology of female breast cancer: an international comparison of screening, incidence, survival and mortality. *Cancer epidemiology*.; 36(3):237-48.